

From Grounding to Planning: Benchmarking Bottlenecks in Web Agents

Segev Shlomov^{a,*}, Ben Wiesel^a, Aviad Sela^a, Ido Levy^a, Liane Galanti^a and Roy Abitbol^a

^aIBM Research, Israel

Abstract. General web-based agents are increasingly essential for interacting with complex web environments, yet their performance in real-world web applications remains poor, yielding extremely low accuracy even with state-of-the-art frontier models. We observe that these agents can be decomposed into two primary components: Planning and Grounding. Yet, most existing research treats these agents as black boxes, focusing on end-to-end evaluations which hinder meaningful improvements. We sharpen the distinction between the planning and grounding components and conduct a novel analysis by refining experiments on the Mind2Web dataset. Our work proposes a new benchmark for each of the two components, identifying the bottlenecks and pain points that limit agent performance. Contrary to prevalent assumptions, our findings suggest that grounding is not a significant bottleneck and can be effectively addressed with current techniques. Instead, the primary challenge lies in the planning component, which is the main source of performance degradation. Through this analysis, we offer new insights and demonstrate practical suggestions for improving the capabilities of web agents, paving the way for more reliable agents.

1 Introduction

Generalized web agents are designed to autonomously navigate and interact with complex web environments, performing tasks that range from simple information retrieval to intricate multi-step procedures [10, 21, 65]. As the demand for automation and intelligent interaction with web interfaces grows, these agents are becoming increasingly crucial in various applications, such as virtual assistants, automated customer service, and copilots [14, 64].

Significant effort has been dedicated to the development of robust and reliable web agents, ranging from the development of specialized large language models (LLMs) tailored for web navigation [10, 64] to the incorporation of state-of-the-art (SOTA) generalist models such as GPT-4 with advanced vision capabilities [21, 64]. Despite these advancements, the performance of web agents in real-world scenarios remains low. These agents frequently fail to achieve reasonable accuracy in completing web-based tasks, raising concerns about their reliability and effectiveness in practical applications [31, 61].

A key challenge lies in the prevalent approach to evaluating web agents, which often treats them as black-box systems and focuses on end-to-end performance metrics [10]. While this approach offers a high-level perspective on agent capabilities, it tends to obscure individual skills and capabilities required for the task, making it difficult to address specific performance issues. In particular, it fails to

distinguish between two core components of web agents: Planning and grounding. Planning refers to the agent’s ability to determine the appropriate sequence of actions to accomplish a given task, while grounding involves correctly identifying and interacting with relevant web elements based on these decisions [64].

Motivated by this understanding, this paper aims to dissect the influence of planning and grounding (i.e., element resolution; unrelated to symbol-grounding in classical AI) on web agents’ performance. By isolating these factors, our research determines which aspect predominantly affects the agents’ ability to complete web-based tasks. This differentiation clarifies pathways for enhancing agent capabilities and provides clearer insights into the optimal allocation of resources within the web-agent’s pipeline. To achieve this, we modified the experimental setup of Mind2Web, implementing controlled variations that isolate the planning and grounding components. Specifically, we introduce two distinct modes of operation. The first, termed high-level, aligns with the traditional method of evaluating agents’ performance on Mind2Web [10]. In this mode, the agent is given a general description of a multi-step task and must determine the correct sequence of actions to complete it. The second, termed low-level, gives the model explicit references to the elements it needs to interact with at each step of the task. This mode aims to isolate the grounding component by eliminating planning.

Our experiments reveal several key conclusions. Contrary to previous assertions [64], planning emerges as the primary bottleneck limiting overall agent performance. We show that even under controlled setup, where models have to choose between merely two elements, of which one is the ground-truth element, accuracy is much lower than expected. Moreover, we find that when grounding is isolated from planning, a near-perfect element accuracy is achieved, highlighting that focusing only on improving grounding techniques through advanced computer vision (CV) or Document Object Model (DOM)-based methods is not sufficient. Furthermore, we find that reducing the number of candidate elements for the agents consistently improves performance, highlighting the importance of effective element filtration and ranking mechanisms in complex web navigation tasks. Our work makes the following key contributions:

- We formalize a clear decomposition of web-based agents into two fundamental components—Planning and Grounding—enabling a shift from black-box evaluation to more targeted, component-wise analysis.
- We present a refined evaluation benchmark based on the Mind2Web dataset, allowing (almost) separate and focused assessment of planning and grounding capabilities. This methodology is extensible to other benchmarks with minimal adaptation.

* Corresponding Author. Email: segev.shlomov1@ibm.com.

- We empirically identify planning as the primary performance bottleneck. Even when enhancing page understanding and improving the ranking mechanism to better support planning, agents still fall short of achieving industry-grade accuracy.

2 Related Work

2.1 General Web Agents

Recent advancements have propelled web-based agents to the forefront of navigating and manipulating complex digital environments. These agents are instrumental in a wide array of automation [58, 38] tasks, including testing, personal assistance [50], data extraction, content management, and enhancing accessibility [56, 2].

The field saw rapid growth, marked by the release of systems like Agent E [1], Agent Q [40], WebPilot [62], AWM [55], SteP [52], WorkArena Agent [15], AutoWebGLM [28], and AutoAgent [53].

Offering diverse tasks across domains to evaluate agent generalizability, decision-making, and robustness in realistic, reproducible environments, this progress was fueled by benchmarks such as Mind2Web [9], Web Voyager [20], Web Linx [33], WebArena [66], Visual Web Arena [26], WorkArena [15], Online Mind2Web, WorkArena++ [3], and [32].

While these benchmarks support end-to-end evaluation in interactive settings, they often obscure the contribution of individual components like planning and grounding. To isolate and study grounding specifically, we required an offline benchmark that provides full access to the DOM, screenshots, and interaction history. Mind2Web uniquely satisfies these requirements, making it particularly suitable for fine-grained analysis of grounding performance.

Despite recent advances, current agents still fall short of the reliability needed for real-world deployment [21, 7, 47, 5, 39, 27]. These agents typically consist of two core components: planning, which acts as the agent’s “mind” to determine next actions, and grounding, which serves as its “eyes and hands” to interpret and execute those actions within the environment. Recent findings, such as those by Zheng et al. [64], suggest that models like GPT-4o may perform effective planning if they are grounded properly—underscoring the need to disentangle and rigorously evaluate each component.

2.2 Grounding

Element grounding is the task of accurately identifying and linking a UI element on a web page, based on a natural language reference name. To do so, the grounder first needs to understand the UI. Semantic UI understanding or as more commonly known, page understanding (PU), plays a critical role in web-based agents, integrating text and image inputs to mimic human capabilities necessary for interacting with graphical user interfaces [4, 22, 54]. Originally dominated by HTML-based parsing [8, 67], this field has evolved through the adoption of LLMs that enhance the parsing and comprehension of complex web UIs [17, 25, 60, 48], despite their shortcomings with dynamic and extensive web applications [36].

Naturally, vision-based soon followed with significant contributions, providing the added benefit of better mimicking the human form of interacting with a web page. Vision-based grounding has evolved from elementary computer vision techniques to more complex models like R-CNN [45, 35] and YOLO [44, 51], which significantly improve the detection and classification of UI elements [6, 57].

The development of large vision language models (LVLMs) represents a major breakthrough, merging vision and linguistic AI to achieve deeper semantic understanding of UIs [11, 43, 42]. Recent

research confirms the superiority of multi-modal LVLMs in specialized grounding tasks over generalist models [63, 7, 34].

The integration of text and vision-based grounding with LLMs and LVLMs marks a significant advancement in web agent technology, enhancing the interface between humans and machines in digital environments. Following the page understanding, the grounder must identify the best match based on the reference element description. This task can be approached using syntactic or semantic matching techniques [49], with some methods leveraging LLMs for improved accuracy [7].

Problem Formulation

We formalize the web agent task as a finite-horizon Markov Decision Process (MDP), where each state s consists of a tuple (DOM, screenshot, history), representing the current web page’s structure, its rendered visual appearance, and the action history so far. The action a is defined as either a text input or a click, taking the form (type, text, id) or (click, id) respectively. An episode ends when a success flag is returned from the test harness, indicating task completion.

To model the agent’s behavior, we decompose it into two core functions: a grounding function $g : (s, r) \rightarrow \text{id}$ that selects a target element ID based on the current state s and a textual reference r (e.g., from the task instruction), and a planner $\pi : (s, \text{goal}^*, C^*) \rightarrow a$ that chooses the next action based on the state s , the structured goal representation goal^* , and auxiliary context C^* (such as pre-planning tips). This formulation allows explicit disentanglement of semantic reference resolution (grounding) from strategic decision-making (planning).

2.3 Planning

Agent planning has transitioned significantly from its initial stage, where rule-based systems, though useful, were often rigid and limited to predefined tasks [16]. The advent of LLMs marked a pivotal shift, enabling more dynamic planning across diverse tasks [24, 19]. A notable advancement was introduced by Nakano et al. [37], who utilized LLMs to parse and respond to queries in a text-based web environment, laying the groundwork for more interactive web agents. Gur et al. [18] further refined this approach by decomposing complex instructions into manageable sub-instructions, enhancing the granularity of task execution.

The planning evolution has since expanded into two main directions: in-context planning, where agents adjust to tasks within a given context [21, 65], and fine-tuned approaches that tailor agent behaviors through specific training regimens [23], such as curriculum-based web trajectory learning [29]. Despite these innovations, fine-tuned models are expensive to train and to collect high-quality data often struggle with scalability and generalization across the vast and varied web environment. Therefore, their practical implementation in real-life applications is still lacking.

3 Grounding

We modified the Mind2Web experimental setup to isolate the action planning from the element grounding. The agent is given a low-level, single-step task and a set of available elements, with the goal of finding (grounding) it by choosing the most suitable element. The Mind2Web dataset was originally planned for evaluating the fulfillment of high-level tasks (e.g., “Find a 3-bedroom apartment to rent

in New York”), using multi-step flows. As such, it does not contain the step-wise instructions serving as the ground truth of each turn in the flow. To that end, we extended Mind2Web so that it is also suitable for evaluating the fulfillment of this low-level task. We used the implicit step-wise data in Mind2Web to extract the action type and the name of the ground truth interacted element for each step in each flow. This results in an augmented dataset containing low-level instructions for each step in Mind2Web.

3.1 Setup

The grounding task requires translating low-level instructions—comprising the action type, element name, and a list of available UI elements—into a direct reference to the ground-truth selected element within the MHTML file. To achieve this, we refined the Mind2Web benchmark by creating new low-level instruction samples.

For the grounding task, we removed¹ samples containing duplicate elements that could not be distinguished when using direct references and corrupted samples where the element name was empty or None (). Our reasoning is that in those cases, even humans would not be able to distinctly locate the right elements. We note that some of the corrupted samples are due to the inherent process of the Mind2Web annotation, as the ground truth element name was collected automatically by the annotator’s demonstration on the web page. This refined benchmark enables rapid iteration across numerous experiments, minimizing the costs of commercial frontier LLMs, and reducing experimental time while maintaining the original characteristics of the Mind2Web benchmark.

For a comprehensive evaluation, we employed three types of PU techniques (CV, JS, DOM), two types of prompts (WebVoy and ours), and two core models (GPT-4o and Llama2). We also tested the original MindAct model on this setting. The accuracy metric is calculated according to the element accuracy in [10]. The entire code base is available at [AnonymouSubmission.git.com], and the full list of samples is included in the supplementary material.

We create an element selection pipeline with a PU node, a syntactic matching node, and a semantic matching node. For the PU node, we compare three implementations: a) Vision-based OCR, referred hereafter as CV, b) Javascript (JS), using WebVoyager’s approach [6], and c) our page understanding (PU) algorithm for extracting candidate elements. We refer to it hereafter as DOM PU, indicating that it utilizes the Document Object Model (DOM) analysis techniques. To ensure an accurate comparison, we use the raw HTML bounding box data collected during the original Mind2Web dataset creation, which reflects the elements as they appeared in the original screen view. Additionally, we analyzed the Mind2Web metadata to exclude steps with action instructions that lacked explicit element references (e.g., instructions involving [svg] and empty reference name), ensuring a more relevant sample.

3.2 WebNaviX’s page understanding

DOM-based PU queries a web page using a predefined set of rules, primarily CSS selectors. These rules were hardened following a rigorous process of analysis and measurement, resulting in a high coverage of the interactable elements on the web page. We further enrich each of the elements with semantic information, extracted from the attributes of the queried element, and other DOM elements that are

¹ We preserve the original characteristics of Mind2Web (cross-task: 20.8%, cross-web: 15.8%, and cross-domain: 63.2%)

related to it in a spatial or hierarchical connection. This information helps to uniquely characterize each element and will be used by the next nodes in the pipeline. We note that the set of rules can be easily extended to new applications, and can even be auto-generated by a simple LLM task [49].

The next pipeline step ranks the extracted candidates using common syntactic matching algorithms [30]. We match the step-level instruction with the semantic attributes of the candidate elements. Following the syntactic matching, we invoke semantic ranking using a sentence transformer (all-mpnet-base-v2). We sort the elements based on the similarity of their embedding against the step-level instruction. Finally, a (v)LLM uses the entire information to select the appropriate element ID for invocation. Aligned with findings in [6], we also implemented a pipeline primarily based on CV techniques, combined with an optical character recognition (OCR) model [46]. This pipeline ingests a capture of a GUI screen (from the Mind2Web subset) and a text used as the reference expression (e.g., “Click Submit” or “Type First Name”). We match the extracted text and assign each element a score [30]. We further utilize a secondary match that considers neighboring elements, based on the assumption that semantic context may stem from nearby elements. Finally, a target click position (x, y coordinate) is generated as output.

Figure 1. Grounding Pipeline: The website’s DOM, screenshot, and low-level instruction are processed through the PU and element ranking phases to generate an annotated screen capture with SoM and a prompt. These are then passed together with the low-level instruction to the VLM to select the web element

3.3 WebVoyager

Building on the work in [21], we utilized WebVoyager’s (WebVoy) code to create an additional experimental pipeline. WebVoy employs a generalist model for both high-level task planning and low-level element grounding. Although originally designed for online applications, we tested WebVoy using the provided code in an offline scenario with the Mind2Web dataset, a context where it had not been previously applied. To address this, we made minimal modifications to the original code to simulate an online interaction, but we preserved the core thought and action prompting as in the original paper. For simplicity and uniformity with other experiments, we reduce the set of permitted actions to click, type, and scroll. Scrolling is emulated by passing different sections of the web page corresponding to the model’s scrolling actions. This approach enables us to evaluate performance on Mind2Web while preserving the core methodology of WebVoy.

Initially, WebVoy employs a set-of-marks (SoM) algorithm [59] to identify candidate UI elements on the screen, drawing boxes around

them, and assigning an ID to each element. The processed image and the textual list of elements are then used in the subsequent phase. For the SoM, WebVoy uses a simple JavaScript (JS) query to extract all interactive elements from the web page. After the SoM step, WebVoy creates a prompt for a LVL (capable of ingesting both text and image, GPT-4o in our setup) which includes the processed SoM image, the list of SoM candidates, and a low-level instruction. Leveraging its visual reasoning capabilities, GPT-4o processes this input data and identifies the ID of the appropriate element. WebVoy completes the step by either interacting with the element or, in offline evaluations, comparing the result to the ground truth.

3.4 Results

As illustrated in Table 1, both our text-only DOM-based algorithm and the GPT-4o vision-based method surpassed 85% accuracy in element grounding. Specifically, our DOM-based algorithm achieved a 90.4% success rate in accurately identifying the correct element, indicating that element grounding is not a significant bottleneck. Additionally, the inclusion of computer vision techniques or a large vision language model resulted in only a slight improvement in accuracy. For instance, when vision was integrated, the accuracy increased marginally from 77.6% to 78.4% on the JS PU, and from 88.3% to 90.4% with our DOM-based PU approach. We attribute this to the inherently well-defined nature of the grounding task, where the primary requirement is to identify the correct reference element. In this context, a visual representation of the entire user interface does not offer substantial additional benefits. Furthermore, there is minimal variation in the base model performance when using a text-only LLM. For example, Llama2 achieved 87.1% accuracy, while GPT-4o reached 88.3%. We also evaluated a computer vision-only approach, which yielded a relatively lower accuracy of 70.2%. This limitation is consistent with challenges in OCR models [57, 41], as they often fail to detect all UI elements on the screen and lack access to crucial metadata (e.g., element type, Aria label, and element role).

Method	Model	Vision	PU	Accuracy
MindAct	GPT-4o	N	DeBERTa	87
WebVoy	GPT-4o	N	JS	77.6
Our	Llama2 70B	N	Our Dom-PU	87.1
Our	GPT-4o	N	Our Dom-PU	88.3
WebVoy	GPT-4o	Y	JS	78.4
Our	GPT-4o	Y	CV	70.2
Our	GPT-4o	Y	Our Dom-PU	90.4

Table 1. Element accuracy results of different methods over the full refined Mind2Web benchmark dataset on the low-level grounding task.

We further manually analyzed the remaining 9.6% of errors and identified that approximately half of them stem from inherent issues within the Mind2Web dataset itself. One common issue involves cases where the task instructs the agent to “click” on a typeable object, such as a text input field, where a typing action would be more appropriate. Additionally, some instructions within the dataset are too vague, lacking sufficient detail to precisely identify the target element. For example, instructions like “Click on 5” do not always specify which attribute or visible text to match, leaving ambiguity that the grounding algorithms struggle to resolve. Another frequent source of error arises from elements nested within other elements, where the ground truth annotation only highlights the inner or outer element,

leading to difficulties in accurately identifying the entire interactive area. These issues are compounded by the fact that the annotations in Mind2Web were created through demonstrations, rather than reflecting how an agent or user would naturally reference the element in a real-world scenario, which can result in subtle discrepancies that impact grounding accuracy. The remaining half of the errors can be attributed to limitations in our current PU algorithmic approach.

4 Planning

Going back to the original settings of Mind2Web, the high-level objective setting is the standard setting of web agents, where a natural language description of the intent is given (e.g., “Order a United flight from NY to SF on Aug 8”) and the agent should act one step at a time and perform the actions required to accomplish the objective. Typically, each step’s input includes the current web page, the past action commands, and the main objective. The output is the type of UI action and a reference (element id) to the element that the agents would like to interact with to accomplish its goal. For analyzing action planning, we use only the subset of 703 successfully grounded samples as a baseline to evaluate planning decisions independently, minimizing grounding-related challenges effect. We tested four models (MindAct, SeeAct, WebVoy, and ours - WebNaviX) with three PU types (JS, DeBERTa, and ours). To ensure a fair comparison and validate the efficiency of the split, we employed two mechanisms: comparing the weighted average results of SOTA models on the original Mind2Web split and projecting their performance onto our split (cross-task: 31.1%, cross-web: 11.52%, and cross-domain: 57.3%).

4.1 MindAct

To ensure consistency, we ground the results on our benchmark dataset split by applying SOTA web navigation methods as a baseline. The first method we use is MindAct [10], which implements a two-stage, text-only web navigation model consisting of candidate generation and action prediction stages. In the first stage, MindAct employs a ranker to select the top 50 elements. Subsequently, the action generation problem is framed as a multiple-choice question-answering task, with the candidate elements serving as options, including a “None” option if the target element is absent. We run the provided code, initially producing ranking results using their DeBERTa model (trained on the entire Mind2Web training dataset). And later, we run either their fine-tuned Flan-T5XL model weights or an in-context learning GPT-4o model for action prediction.

4.2 SeeAct

We include results from SeeAct [64] to provide context for our large vision-language approach. However, since the provided SeeAct code is only suitable for online evaluation, we project the performance on the offline dataset by calculating a weighted average of the respective results on cross-task, cross-website, and cross-domain using their relative presence on the new split.

4.2.1 WebVoyager

We used the same method as described in Section 3.3. However, as opposed to the grounding experiment, in this planning setup, we prompt the LLM with the high-level text describing the task.

4.3 WebNaviX

Our agent’s first step is applying the DOM-Based PU as described in the grounding task (Section 3.2). Thereafter, the results of the DOM-PU are ranked using semantic similarity (as discussed in Section 3.2). The resulting elements are then transformed into a SoM list of candidates and embedded (like in WebVoyager) in the prompt of the LVLm together with the history of past actions, and the high-level task description. The LVLm planner returns the predicted action: Type or click, and the predicted element ID. If the action is type, the planner also provides the required value for typing in.

Figure 2. WebNaviX Architecture: The website’s DOM, screenshot, and high-level instruction are processed through the PU and element ranking phase equipped with an improved ranking to generate an annotated screen capture with SoM and a prompt. These are then passed together with the high-level instruction and history of actions to the VLM to select the web element.

4.4 Results

Table 2 presents the results of action planning using various approaches. We focus solely on element accuracy, omitting the Operation-F1 and Step Success Rate (Step-SR) metrics used in [10]. Our analysis reveals that selecting the correct operation is relatively straightforward and can often be inferred from the type of the selected element. Therefore, we consider the element accuracy as the most significant metric that directly correlates with the Step-SR.

To ensure the validity of our experiments, we compare the performance of SOTA models on our benchmark split with their original results. On our split, MindAct FlanT5XL projects an accuracy of 46.53%, calculated as a weighted average across cross-task (31.1%), cross-web (11.52%), and cross-domain (57.3%) subsets. The actual result on our split was 46.75%. MindAct GPT4 projects an accuracy of 36.45%, where the actual result on our split is 36.27%, showing insignificant differences from the projection.

As shown in Table 2, the current SOTA MindAct FlanT5 model demonstrates strong performance on our Mind2Web split. This is primarily due to our split containing more cross-task content, which plays to the strengths of fine-tuned models. However, fine-tuned models show reduced effectiveness in cross-website and cross-domain evaluations. Furthermore, the process of fine-tuning models for specific tasks, websites, or domains requires large training data and can be resource-intensive, potentially limiting their practical applicability and generalizability.

In contrast, our analysis of in-context learning models reveals that for text-based methods (Vision=N), our agent WebNaviX, utilizing the DOM-based PU technique with the ranking mechanism and the WebVoyager’s prompt, yields the best result (40.68%). Notably, it

Base Method	Model	Vision	PU	Accuracy
Supervised Fine-Tuning				
MindAct	Flan-T5L	N	DeBERTa	44.10
MindAct	Flan-T5XL	N	DeBERTa	46.75
In-Context Learning				
MindAct	GPT-4o	N	DeBERTa	36.27
WebVoy	GPT-4o	N	JS	27
WebVoy	GPT-4o	N	Our-PU	32.3
WebNaviX	Lamma3 70B	N	Our-PU	35.13
WebNaviX	GPT-4o	N	Our-PU	40.68*
WebVoy	GPT-4o	Y	JS	32.86
WebVoy	GPT-4o	Y	Our-PU	36.96
SeeAct	GPT-4o	Y	DeBERTa	43.1
WebNaviX	GPT-4o	Y	Our-PU	47.37
WebNaviX +R	GPT-4o	Y	Our-PU	49.08*

Table 2. Element accuracy results of different methods over the benchmark dataset in high-level setting. WebNaviX significantly outperforms SOTA methods. Vision techniques are essential for in-context web agents. The supervised methods involve fine-tuning of the underlying model.

outperforms the JS technique from WebVoy, demonstrating the efficacy of our PU method. For vision-based models, our agent WebNaviX achieves significant (Wilcoxon Signed-Rank test [12, 13], $p < 0.05$) improvement over existing state-of-the-art methods without relying on data-specific fine-tuning. Using our method allows you to avoid task-specific fine-tuning while maintaining consistent performance across diverse splits, thereby addressing the key limitation of previous approaches.

4.5 Planning is the main bottleneck

A critical challenge faced by LLMs in web-based agents is their ability to effectively plan actions based on a list of relevant UI elements. The planner component, which is responsible for selecting the next element to interact with, frequently struggles to make accurate decisions, even when provided with a narrowed list of options. To further investigate this issue, we conduct a series of experiments where the ground truth element is explicitly injected into the list of choices presented to the planner (Oracle Ranker). We tested the planner’s performance by varying the number of relevant UI elements, focusing on its ability to correctly identify the ground truth when it is guaranteed to be included in its list of options. This manipulation helps isolate the impact of the planning algorithm from grounding or element ranking challenges.

The result, as can be seen in the Oracle Ranker column on Table 4, reveals a surprising and concerning trend. Even when the planner is tasked with choosing between just two elements, one of which is the ground truth, it only achieves an accuracy of 86%. Given the narrow decision space, we consider this to be a low rate of accuracy. It serves as a testament to the fact that the planner struggles to make the right choice, even under a simplified setup, let alone under more complex conditions. These findings suggest that the current planning mechanisms within LLMs are insufficient for achieving the high accuracy required in complex web environments. Contrary to the paper [64] titled “GPT-4V(ision) is a Generalist Web Agent, if Grounded”, our results show that currently LVLms cannot act as web agents, even if perfectly grounded. We argue that additional external knowledge may be necessary to enhance the planner’s capabilities. Without such improvements, the planning phase remains a substantial bottleneck,

limiting the overall effectiveness of web-based agents.

Figure 3. Planner performance across task flow steps.

We further conducted an analysis of the planner’s performance by examining how its accuracy varied across different step positions within the task flow. We initially hypothesized that the accuracy might be low in the early steps, since there are multiple correct ways to initiate tasks but only one is annotated as ground truth. In the final steps, where the planner would have accumulated enough context from previous steps, we expected high performance. As shown in Figure 3, the accuracy forms a U-shaped pattern, with better performance at the start and end of the task flow, and a small dip in the middle. This consistent behavior across multiple ranking numbers suggests that mid-task complexity and variability pose more challenges for the planner.

4.6 Improving Ranking Heuristics

To enhance the candidate generation process, we explored additional ranking heuristics beyond semantic similarity. We observed that most ground truth candidates in the Mind2Web training dataset are short, with 92% containing less than 6 words. To counter this bias, we divided the candidates into three groups: up to 3 words, 4-6 words, and 7+ words. Elements were then sampled from each group in descending order of semantic similarity, while enforcing a sampling distribution corresponding to the natural distribution of text lengths. This approach improved the recall of ground truth elements (see the +Length row in Table 3).

4.6.1 Location-based Heuristic

We observed that the ground truth elements tend to cluster towards the top and left sides of pages (Figure 4). To address this spatial bias, we split candidates into two groups based on their Y-axis positions: Up to 700 pixels and above 700 pixels. We then implemented an over-sampling strategy for elements from the 0-700 px group with a 0.92 sampling ratio. Combining these length and location strategies yielded further improvements in recall rates (see the +Length+Location row in Table 3).

4.6.2 Performance Comparison

Table 4 illustrates the substantial impact of the improved ranker on overall performance. The +Length+Location method consistently outperforms the semantic only approach across all candidate set sizes, with the optimal set size emerging as 30 candidates. Notably, the +Length+Location method exhibits a more plateaued pattern,

Figure 4. Spatial distribution of the ground truth element relative to the page layouts, within the training dataset. Lower Y values indicate proximity to the top of the page and lower X values indicate proximity to the left side of the page. Colors indicate the length of the text.

suggesting early identification of relevant candidates and reducing the need for large candidate sets. While the fine-tuned DeBERTa-based ranker from MindAct slightly outperformed our approach, our ranker offers significant advantages in flexibility and generalizability, requiring no specific fine-tuning. This characteristic makes our approach adaptable to diverse datasets and domains, potentially offering superior performance in rapidly evolving real-world applications.

Ranking Method	Number of Candidates			
	20	30	50	70
Semantic only	54	64	74	80
+Length	62	69	80	85
+Location	72	80	93	95
+Length+Location	73	83	92	96
+Location+Step	72	81	94	97
+Length+Location+Step	75	85	94	97
MindAct	84.6	-	93.8	-

Table 3. Recall rates % of different ranking methods across varying numbers of candidates.

Candidates Number	Semantic Only	+Length +Location	Oracle Ranker
2	-	-	86.05
5	-	-	75.25
10	32.43	43.67	70.41
20	38.55	47.94	63.72
30	40.11	49.08	62.30
50	43.10	48.65	57.75
All	47.37	47.37	47.37

Table 4. Element accuracy comparison using different ranking methods, across different numbers of candidates. The Oracle ranker column corresponds to WebNaviX result with the ground true injected into the list of UI elements.

5 Discussion

We isolate planning and grounding components by conducting controlled experiments on a new refined Mind2Web benchmark. Our

results indicate that the primary bottleneck is the model’s planning capabilities. We believe that simply using a "smarter" model, more computational power, or a more advanced frontier model, or even improving grounding to perfection, will have a limited impact on accuracy in real-world web agents. Instead, we hypothesize that the main gap lies in external knowledge. Incorporating additional knowledge and context into the planner, particularly in business applications, could bridge the gap between abstract task descriptions and concrete, step-by-step actions.

Building on this premise, we experimented with a simple modification to our algorithm: a single call to an LLM at the outset of each workflow. This LLM is tasked with generating a high-level pre-plan for task completion, constrained to a concise paragraph. This pre-plan is then appended to the prompt of each step in the flow when the LLM is called upon to select the optimal candidate. Using this simple method, the performance improved marginally (51.7%). This improvement, although not significant, suggests the potential benefits of embedding additional context in planning decisions and hints at the value of a broader strategic overview guiding action sequences. Further research is needed to fully understand the implications and reliability of this approach.

5.1 Threats to Validity

We selected Mind2Web for our experiments because it is the first widely adopted large-scale dataset derived from real websites, providing a diverse and representative set of tasks for real-world web interactions. However, it is important to acknowledge our limitations.

We did not perform an exhaustive hyperparameter optimization. However, this aligns with our research objectives, which prioritize assessing fundamental planning and reasoning capabilities over achieving peak performance. Although we were able to beat the SOTA models this is not the main goal of the paper. We selected and rigorously tested SOTA models for their reasoning abilities, providing a strong baseline and realistic results. We argue that if these frontier models show low planning performance, it is likely that other models would struggle even more. In addition, while fine-tuned SOTA models may achieve performance close to our technique, they require training data and struggle with cross-domain tasks. Although these methods can boost performance in specific contexts, their limitations highlight the need for more generalized approaches that can adapt across diverse domains.

Our study is based on offline experiments, which may not fully capture the dynamic nature of live web environments. This discrepancy could lead to potential differences between our experimental results and real-world performance. To mitigate this limitation, we carefully adapted algorithms to function effectively in an offline setting, striving to maintain the integrity of the original methods. However, we acknowledge that these adaptations may not entirely replicate the complexities of live environments. Additionally, we chose not to test against environments like WebArena, as they conflate planning and grounding tasks. While such datasets are valuable for overall agent assessment, our focus on isolating grounding from planning was critical for pinpointing the root causes of performance deficits in web interaction tasks.

Acknowledgments

This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon research and innovation program under grant agreement no 101120218 (HumAIne).

References

- [1] T. Abuelsaad, D. Akkil, P. Dey, A. Jagmohan, A. Vempaty, and R. Kokku. Agent-e: From autonomous web navigation to foundational design principles in agentic systems. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2407.13032*, 2024.
- [2] S. N. Akter, Z. Yu, A. Muhamed, T. Ou, A. Bäuerle, Á. A. Cabrera, K. Dholakia, C. Xiong, and G. Neubig. An in-depth look at gemini’s language abilities. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2312.11444*, 2023.
- [3] L. Boisvert, M. Thakkar, M. Gasse, M. Caccia, T. Le Sellier De Chezelles, Q. Cappart, N. Chapados, A. Lacoste, and A. Drouin. Workarena++: Towards compositional planning and reasoning-based common knowledge work tasks. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2407.05291*, 2024.
- [4] J. M. Carroll. *HCI models, theories, and frameworks: Toward a multidisciplinary science*. Elsevier, 2003.
- [5] B. Chen, C. Shu, E. Shareghi, N. Collier, K. Narasimhan, and S. Yao. Fireact: Toward language agent fine-tuning. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2310.05915*, 2023.
- [6] J. Chen, M. Xie, Z. Xing, C. Chen, X. Xu, L. Zhu, and G. Li. Object detection for graphical user interface: Old fashioned or deep learning or a combination? In *proceedings of the 28th ACM joint meeting on European Software Engineering Conference and Symposium on the Foundations of Software Engineering*, pages 1202–1214, 2020.
- [7] K. Cheng, Q. Sun, Y. Chu, F. Xu, L. YanTao, J. Zhang, and Z. Wu. Seeclck: Harnessing gui grounding for advanced visual gui agents. In *ICLR 2024 Workshop on Large Language Model (LLM) Agents*, 2024.
- [8] X. Deng, P. Shiralkar, C. Lockard, B. Huang, and H. Sun. Domlm: Learning generalizable representations for html documents. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2201.10608*, 2022.
- [9] X. Deng, Y. Gu, B. Zheng, S. Chen, S. Stevens, B. Wang, H. Sun, and Y. Su. Mind2web: Towards a generalist agent for the web. In *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems (NeurIPS)*, volume 36, 2024.
- [10] X. Deng, Y. Gu, B. Zheng, S. Chen, S. Stevens, B. Wang, H. Sun, and Y. Su. Mind2web: Towards a generalist agent for the web. *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems*, 36, 2024.
- [11] A. Dosovitskiy, L. Beyer, A. Kolesnikov, D. Weissenborn, X. Zhai, T. Unterthiner, M. Dehghani, M. Minderer, G. Heigold, S. Gelly, et al. An image is worth 16x16 words: Transformers for image recognition at scale. In *International Conference on Learning Representations*, 2020.
- [12] R. Dror, G. Baumer, S. Shlomov, and R. Reichart. The hitchhiker’s guide to testing statistical significance in natural language processing. In *Proceedings of the 56th annual meeting of the association for computational linguistics (volume 1: Long papers)*, pages 1383–1392, 2018.
- [13] R. Dror, L. Peled-Cohen, S. Shlomov, and R. Reichart. *Statistical significance testing for natural language processing*. Springer, 2020.
- [14] A. Drouin, M. Gasse, M. Caccia, I. H. Laradji, M. Del Verme, T. Marty, L. Boisvert, M. Thakkar, Q. Cappart, D. Vazquez, et al. Workarena: How capable are web agents at solving common knowledge work tasks? *arXiv preprint arXiv:2403.07718*, 2024.
- [15] A. Drouin, M. Gasse, M. Caccia, I. H. Laradji, M. Del Verme, T. Marty, L. Boisvert, M. Thakkar, Q. Cappart, D. Vazquez, N. Chapados, and A. Lacoste. Workarena: How capable are web agents at solving common knowledge work tasks? *arXiv preprint arXiv:2403.07718*, 2024.
- [16] D. Ferrucci, E. Brown, J. Chu-Carroll, J. Fan, D. Gondek, A. Kalyanpur, A. Lally, J. W. Murdock, E. Nyberg, J. Prager, N. Schlaefer, and C. Welty. Building watson: An overview of the deepqa project. *AI Magazine*, 31:59–79, 09 2010. doi: 10.1609/aimag.v31i13.2303.
- [17] I. Gür, O. Nachum, Y. Miao, M. Safdari, A. Huang, A. Chowdhery, S. Narang, N. Fiedel, and A. Faust. Understanding html with large language models. In *Findings of the Association for Computational Linguistics: EMNLP 2023*, pages 2803–2821, 2023.
- [18] I. Gur, H. Furuta, A. V. Huang, M. Safdari, Y. Matsuo, D. Eck, and A. Faust. A real-world webagent with planning, long context understanding, and program synthesis. In *The Twelfth International Conference on Learning Representations*, 2024. URL <https://openreview.net/forum?id=9JQtrumvg8>.
- [19] K. Guu, K. Lee, Z. Tung, P. Pasupat, and M. Chang. Retrieval augmented language model pre-training. In *International conference on machine learning*, pages 3929–3938. PMLR, 2020.
- [20] H. He, W. Yao, K. Ma, W. Yu, Y. Dai, H. Zhang, Z. Lan, and D. Yu. Webvoyager: Building an end-to-end web agent with large multimodal models. In *Proceedings of the 62nd Annual Meeting of the Association for Computational Linguistics (ACL)*, pages 6864–6890, 2024.
- [21] H. He, W. Yao, K. Ma, W. Yu, Y. Dai, H. Zhang, Z. Lan, and D. Yu. Webvoyager: Building an end-to-end web agent with large multimodal models. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2401.13919*, 2024.

- [22] M. Hegarty. The cognitive science of visual-spatial displays: Implications for design. *Topics in cognitive science*, 3(3):446–474, 2011.
- [23] W. Hong, W. Wang, Q. Lv, J. Xu, W. Yu, J. Ji, Y. Wang, Z. Wang, Y. Dong, M. Ding, et al. Cogagent: A visual language model for gui agents. In *Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition*, pages 14281–14290, 2024.
- [24] V. Karpukhin, B. Oguz, S. Min, P. Lewis, L. Wu, S. Edunov, D. Chen, and W.-t. Yih. Dense passage retrieval for open-domain question answering. In B. Webber, T. Cohn, Y. He, and Y. Liu, editors, *Proceedings of the 2020 Conference on Empirical Methods in Natural Language Processing (EMNLP)*, pages 6769–6781, Online, Nov. 2020. Association for Computational Linguistics. doi: 10.18653/v1/2020.emnlp-main.550. URL <https://aclanthology.org/2020.emnlp-main.550>.
- [25] G. Kim, P. Baldi, and S. McAleer. Language models can solve computer tasks. *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems*, 36, 2024.
- [26] J. Y. Koh, R. Lo, L. Jang, V. Duvvur, M. C. Lim, P.-Y. Huang, G. Neubig, S. Zhou, R. Salakhutdinov, and D. Fried. Visualwebarena: Evaluating multimodal agents on realistic visual web tasks. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2401.13649*, 2024.
- [27] J. Y. Koh, S. McAleer, D. Fried, and R. Salakhutdinov. Tree search for language model agents. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2407.01476*, 2024.
- [28] H. Lai, X. Liu, I. L. Iong, S. Yao, Y. Chen, P. Shen, H. Yu, H. Zhang, X. Zhang, Y. Dong, et al. Autowebglm: A large language model-based web navigating agent. In *Proceedings of the 30th ACM SIGKDD Conference on Knowledge Discovery and Data Mining (KDD)*, pages 5295–5306, 2024.
- [29] H. Lai, X. Liu, I. L. Iong, S. Yao, Y. Chen, P. Shen, H. Yu, H. Zhang, X. Zhang, Y. Dong, et al. Autowebglm: Bootstrap and reinforce a large language model-based web navigating agent. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2404.03648*, 2024.
- [30] V. I. Levenshtein et al. Binary codes capable of correcting deletions, insertions, and reversals. In *Soviet physics doklady*, volume 10, pages 707–710. Soviet Union, 1966.
- [31] E. Li and J. Waldo. Websuite: Systematically evaluating why web agents fail. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2406.01623*, 2024.
- [32] X. Liu, H. Yu, H. Zhang, Y. Xu, X. Lei, H. Lai, Y. Gu, H. Ding, K. Men, K. Yang, et al. Agentbench: Evaluating llms as agents. In *The Twelfth International Conference on Learning Representations*, 2023.
- [33] X. H. Lu, Z. Kasner, and S. Reddy. Weblinx: Real-world website navigation with multi-turn dialogue. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2402.05930*, 2024.
- [34] X. H. Lu, Z. Kasner, and S. Reddy. Weblinx: Real-world website navigation with multi-turn dialogue. In *Forty-first International Conference on Machine Learning*, 2024.
- [35] D. Manandhar, H. Jin, and J. Collomosse. Magic layouts: Structural prior for component detection in user interface designs. In *Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition*, pages 15809–15818, 2021.
- [36] R. Mitchell. *Web scraping with Python: Collecting more data from the modern web*. " O'Reilly Media, Inc.", 2018.
- [37] R. Nakano, J. Hilton, S. Balaji, J. Wu, L. Ouyang, C. Kim, C. Hesse, S. Jain, V. Kosaraju, W. Saunders, et al. Webgpt: Browser-assisted question-answering with human feedback. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2112.09332*, 2021.
- [38] A. Oved, S. Shlomov, S. Zeltyn, N. Mashkif, and A. Yaeli. Snap: semantic stories for next activity prediction. In *Proceedings of the AAAI Conference on Artificial Intelligence*, volume 39, pages 28871–28877, 2025.
- [39] J. Pan, Y. Zhang, N. Tomlin, Y. Zhou, S. Levine, and A. Suhr. Autonomous evaluation and refinement of digital agents, 2024.
- [40] P. Putta, E. Mills, N. Garg, S. Motwani, C. Finn, D. Garg, and R. Rafailov. Agent q: Advanced reasoning and learning for autonomous ai agents. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2408.07199*, 2024.
- [41] J. Qian, Y. Ma, C. Lin, and L. Chen. Accelerating ocr-based widget localization for test automation of gui applications. In *Proceedings of the 37th IEEE/ACM International Conference on Automated Software Engineering*, pages 1–13, 2022.
- [42] A. Radford, J. W. Kim, C. Hallacy, A. Ramesh, G. Goh, S. Agarwal, G. Sastry, A. Askell, P. Mishkin, J. Clark, et al. Learning transferable visual models from natural language supervision. In *International conference on machine learning*, pages 8748–8763. PMLR, 2021.
- [43] A. Ramesh, M. Pavlov, G. Goh, S. Gray, C. Voss, A. Radford, M. Chen, and I. Sutskever. Zero-shot text-to-image generation. In *International Conference on Machine Learning*, pages 8821–8831. PMLR, 2021.
- [44] J. Redmon, S. Divvala, R. Girshick, and A. Farhadi. You only look once: Unified, real-time object detection. In *Proceedings of the IEEE conference on computer vision and pattern recognition*, pages 779–788, 2016.
- [45] S. Ren, K. He, R. Girshick, and J. Sun. Faster r-cnn: Towards real-time object detection with region proposal networks. *Advances in neural information processing systems*, 28, 2015.
- [46] D. Rotman, O. Azulai, I. Shapira, Y. Burshtein, and U. Barzelay. Detection masking for improved ocr on noisy documents. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2205.08257*, 2022.
- [47] S. Schwartz, A. Yaeli, and S. Shlomov. Enhancing trust in llm-based ai automation agents: New considerations and future challenges. In *International Joint Conference on Artificial Intelligence*, 2023.
- [48] T. Shi, A. Karpathy, L. Fan, J. Hernandez, and P. Liang. World of bits: An open-domain platform for web-based agents. In *Proceedings of the 34th International Conference on Machine Learning*, 2017.
- [49] S. Shlomov, S. Marreed, and A. Yaeli. Towards a resilient intelligent automation system. In K. Larson, editor, *Proceedings of the Thirty-Third International Joint Conference on Artificial Intelligence, IJCAI-24*, pages 8797–8800. International Joint Conferences on Artificial Intelligence Organization, 8 2024. doi: 10.24963/ijcai.2024/1035. URL <https://doi.org/10.24963/ijcai.2024/1035>. Demo Track.
- [50] S. Shlomov, A. Yaeli, S. Marreed, S. Schwartz, N. Eder, O. Akrabi, and S. Zeltyn. Ida: Breaking barriers in no-code ui automation through large language models and human-centric design. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2407.15673*, 2024.
- [51] M. K. Singh, W. M. Fernandes, and M. S. Rashid. Robust ui automation using deep learning and optical character recognition (ocr). In *Proceedings of International Conference on Recent Trends in Machine Learning, IoT, Smart Cities and Applications: ICMISC 2020*, pages 33–44. Springer, 2021.
- [52] P. Sodhi, S. R. K. Branavan, Y. Artzi, and R. McDonald. Step: Stacked llm policies for web actions. In *Proceedings of the First Conference on Language Modeling (CLaM)*, 2024.
- [53] J. Tang, T. Fan, and C. Huang. Autoagent: A fully-automated and zero-code framework for llm agents. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2502.05957*, 2025.
- [54] M. Turk. Multimodal interaction: A review. *Pattern recognition letters*, 36:189–195, 2014.
- [55] Z. Z. Wang, J. Mao, D. Fried, and G. Neubig. Agent workflow memory. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2409.07429*, 2024.
- [56] Z. Xi, W. Chen, X. Guo, W. He, Y. Ding, B. Hong, M. Zhang, J. Wang, S. Jin, E. Zhou, et al. The rise and potential of large language model based agents: A survey. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2309.07864*, 2023.
- [57] M. Xie, S. Feng, Z. Xing, J. Chen, and C. Chen. Uied: a hybrid tool for gui element detection. In *Proceedings of the 28th ACM Joint Meeting on European Software Engineering Conference and Symposium on the Foundations of Software Engineering*, pages 1655–1659, 2020.
- [58] A. Yaeli, S. Shlomov, A. Oved, S. Zeltyn, and N. Mashkif. Recommending next best skill in conversational robotic process automation. In *International Conference on Business Process Management*, pages 215–230. Springer, 2022.
- [59] J. Yang, H. Zhang, F. Li, X. Zou, C. Li, and J. Gao. Set-of-mark prompting unleashes extraordinary visual grounding in gpt-4v. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2310.11441*, 2023.
- [60] D. Yin, F. Brahma, A. Ravichander, K. Chandu, K.-W. Chang, Y. Choi, and B. Y. Lin. Lumos: Learning agents with unified data, modular design, and open-source llms. In *ICLR 2024 Workshop on Large Language Model (LLM) Agents*, 2023.
- [61] O. Yorann, S. J. Amouyal, C. Malaviya, B. Bogin, O. Press, and J. Berant. Assistantbench: Can web agents solve realistic and time-consuming tasks? *arXiv preprint arXiv:2407.15711*, 2024.
- [62] Y. Zhang, Z. Ma, Y. Ma, Z. Han, Y. Wu, and V. Tresp. Webpilot: A versatile and autonomous multi-agent system for web task execution with strategic exploration. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2408.15978*, 2024.
- [63] Z. Zhang, W. Xie, X. Zhang, and Y. Lu. Reinforced ui instruction grounding: Towards a generic ui task automation api. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2310.04716*, 2023.
- [64] B. Zheng, B. Gou, J. Kil, H. Sun, and Y. Su. Gpt-4v(ision) is a generalist web agent, if grounded. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2401.01614*, 2024.
- [65] S. Zhou, F. F. Xu, H. Zhu, X. Zhou, R. Lo, A. Sridhar, X. Cheng, T. Ou, Y. Bisk, D. Fried, et al. Webarena: A realistic web environment for building autonomous agents. In *The Twelfth International Conference on Learning Representations*, 2023.
- [66] S. Zhou, F. F. Xu, H. Zhu, X. Zhou, R. Lo, A. Sridhar, X. Cheng, T. Ou, Y. Bisk, D. Fried, et al. Webarena: A realistic web environment for building autonomous agents. In *Proceedings of the 12th International Conference on Learning Representations (ICLR)*, 2024.
- [67] Y. Zhou, Y. Sheng, N. Vo, N. Edmonds, and S. Tata. Simplified dom trees for transferable attribute extraction from the web. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2101.02415*, 2021.

Appendix

A Mitigating Text Length Bias in Semantic Matching

Our analysis revealed a bias in the LLM’s candidate selection towards elements with longer texts. We hypothesize that this bias stems from the typically lengthy high-level task descriptions (usually at least one sentence), leading the naive semantic similarity ranker to favor candidates with longer text. However, the majority of ground truth candidates on the original Mind2Web training dataset are actually quite short, with 92% of the samples containing less than 6 words.

To address this discrepancy, we introduced a counter-bias mechanism. We divided the candidates into three groups based on their text length: up to 3 words, 4-6 words, and 7+ words. When generating candidates, we sample elements from each group in descending order of semantic similarity, while enforcing a sampling distribution that corresponds to the natural distribution of text lengths. This approach effectively up-samples shorter words.

The efficacy of this method is evident in the results. The "+Length" ranking method shows a significant improvement in the recall of ground truth elements (i.e., the percentage of times the ground truth element was included in the candidates list). For instance, with 50 candidates, the accuracy improves from 74% (Semantic only) to 80% (+Length). This improvement is consistent across different numbers of candidates, demonstrating the robustness of our length-aware sampling approach.

Figure 5. Frequency histogram of the number of words in the ground truth text on the Mind2Web training dataset.

B Element Grounding Using DOM Parsing

To facilitate robust web element grounding, we utilized a set of CSS Selector rules, outlined in Figure 6. These rules target specific DOM elements, enhancing the accuracy of element identification during DOM-based parsing operations. Each rule defines a unique CSS Selector, ensuring high coverage across varied web pages and applications. Below we describe key rules employed in our experiments:

- **Form Elements:** Target forms with complex layouts or modal dialogs, colored in red for critical interaction points (`form`, `.records-layout-section`, `div[role="dialog"]`).

- **Table Rows:** Blue-coded selectors (`tbody tr`) to parse data tables efficiently.
- **Navigation Tabs:** Aqua-colored selectors for navigation elements (`nav[role="tablist"]`).
- **Input Fields:** Various inputs including text, search, and textarea are highlighted with maroon, crucial for form interactions (`input[type="text"]`, `input[type="search"]`, `input[type="textarea"]`).
- **Selection Controls:** Checkbox and radio inputs are distinctly styled in olive and purple, respectively, for clear visibility and interaction (`input[type='checkbox']`, `input[type='radio']`).
- **Links and Buttons:** Non-advertorial links and actionable buttons are tagged in teal and green, promoting straightforward navigation and actions (`a:not(:has(img))`, `button`).

These rules ensure comprehensive coverage and precise targeting within a DOM, facilitating the subsequent syntactic and semantic matching processes crucial for effective element grounding.

```
-- name: group_rule
selector: form, records-record-layout-section, div[role="dialog"]
color: red
type: form
-- name: group_rule
selector: tbody tr
color: blue
type: table_row
-- name: group_rule
selector: thead tr
color: green
type: table_header
-- name: group_rule
selector: nav, div[role="tablist"]
color: aqua
type: navigation
-- name: group_rule
selector: .jobreqcard, .rcmIntwCandCard
color: aqua
section_name: card
type: section
-- name: rule
selector: input[type="text"], input[type="search"], input[type="textarea"], div[role="textbox"]
color: Maroon
type: input
-- name: rule
selector: input[type='checkbox'], .fd-checkbox_label-container
color: olive
type: checkbox
-- name: rule
selector: input[type='radio'], .inputRC
color: purple
type: radio
-- name: rule
selector: a:not(:has(a)), [role="link"], a .primaryLabel
color: teal
type: link
-- name: rule
selector: label, legend, .field_label span.text
color: black
type: label
-- name: rule
selector: select, .CustomFilter__dropdown, [role="combobox"], .MuiSelect-select
color: orange
type: select_toggle
-- name: rule
selector: option, [role="option"]
color: pink
type: select_option
-- name: rule
selector: button, input[type='button'], input[type='submit'], [role="button"], [onclick]
color: green
type: button
```

Figure 6. CSS Selector rules used for DOM-based web element grounding

C Hyperparameters

C.1 Setting of Hyperparameters

We employed a variety of models with specific hyperparameters optimized for each task. For the GPT-4o model on the OpenAI API, parameters were set as follows: `max_tokens` to 128K, `temperature` and `top_p` both at 1, with `frequency_penalty` and `presence_penalty` at 0. We used a `batch_size` of 1, and configured the API calls to allow up to 10 retries with a timeout of 60 seconds.

C.2 DOM Grounding and Planning

For the DOM Grounding (Dom-PU) task, we used the llama-2-70b model, specifying a greedy decoding method, temperature of 0.1, and a maximum of 20 new tokens. DOM Planning utilized meta-llama/llama-3-70b-instruct with a token range of 1 to 200. Both settings employed policies with a threshold of 0.75, reflecting input and output considerations.

Hyperparameter selection was based on the criterion of maximizing performance results. Despite the high cost of experimentation, which restricted extensive parameter tuning, there is a wide range and number of values tested.

D MIND2WEB Dataset

MIND2WEB (<https://osu-nlp-group.github.io/Mind2Web/> dataset [10]) serves as a benchmark for the development of generalist agents that interpret and execute language-driven instructions across a spectrum of real-world websites. It composed of 2,350 open-ended tasks sourced from 137 websites across 31 diverse domains such as travel, shopping, and services. It stands out by employing actual web environments rather than simulations, capturing the complexity of modern interfaces and user interactions.

Tasks range from simple queries to complex sequences that require navigation, transaction, or data analysis, providing a rich tapestry of user interactions. Each task is accompanied by natural language descriptions, annotated sequences of actions, and comprehensive web page snapshots—HTML, DOM trees, screenshots, and network traffic—documenting each step.

The generalization capability of agents is tested through an evaluation framework that includes cross-task, cross-website, and cross-domain challenges. This framework assesses agents’ ability to adapt to unseen tasks, new websites within familiar domains, and completely novel domains.

E Benchmark Data Set

The list of data samples is included in our supplementary code. After extracting the code, you’ll find a single CSV file in the ‘data’ folder, listing all the samples, including those with duplicate elements where one is the ground truth. In the ‘supplement’ folder, you’ll find two result dataframes: ‘grounding_failures_no_duplicate.csv,’ which includes failed samples without duplicates, and ‘grounding_no_duplicates.csv,’ which contains all samples without duplicates.

F Benchmark Data Curation

We analyzed 8,628 samples from the Mind2Web Test dataset, out of which our DOM SUIU failed to execute on 487 test cases, representing approximately 5.64% of the dataset. Root cause analysis revealed that these failures were due to corrupt MHTML files and missing “node-buckeye-id” annotations with corresponding “action_uid” annotations. We focused only on positive candidates, excluding negative ones, to validate that our SUIU algorithm correctly assigns bounding box values consistent with the calculations performed during the Mind2Web dataset creation. This mapping of our SUIU candidate elements to Mind2Web’s identified positive elements is a crucial step in establishing the SUIU ground truth for our end-to-end experiment.

To ensure accuracy, we computed the bounding box Jaccard Index along with additional features to confidently identify a SUIU element as a ground truth positive candidate. In the course of this analysis, we further excluded 1,779 test cases: 956 samples were dropped because their comparison features fell below the required threshold, with further analysis indicating that these failures were due to significant horizontal or vertical skew. This discrepancy appears to stem from differences in rendering between our desktop environment and the MHTML sampling done during Mind2Web dataset generation. Additionally, 823 samples were excluded because the ground truth positive candidate specified by Mind2Web was not present among the SUIU-extracted candidate elements.

Ultimately, we were left with 6,362 valid test cases for our experiment, where each set of candidate elements from our SUIU included the target ground truth element marked by a dedicated attribute.

From these verified test cases, we sampled a 15% subset, resulting in 995 meaningful samples that maintained a distribution comparable across all test splits.

During our grounding evaluation, we identified 218 samples—approximately 21% of the total—that highlight a significant challenge in planning tasks: the presence of duplicates. A sample is considered a duplicate if the ground truth element has one or more identical additional elements that can cause current solutions to fail without any additional external knowledge. In Figure 8, for example, the application contains duplicate clickable elements—a button and a link, both labeled “Jobs.” This duplication poses a challenge for both grounding and planning, as selecting between the two becomes a matter of chance, with success rates depending on a coin flip. We plan to address this challenge in future work.

It’s worth noting that our analysis also revealed that the Mind2Web Test and Train splits each contain a similar percentage of duplicates, both around 21%.

G Grounding Error Analysis

We identify the root causes and categorize the errors into two main groups: 35% of the errors were due to gaps in our own algorithm, while the remaining 65% were attributed to inherent issues within the Mind2Web dataset.

The algorithmic gaps we identified include some relatively simple problems that can be addressed with minor adjustments, while others require more complex or in-depth solutions. A detailed discussion of these gaps will be addressed in other venues.

The inherent issues within the Mind2Web dataset were further classified into several core problems, including clickable objects, ambiguous target elements, nested elements (“box in a box”) and offline flow equal trajectories to success. Each of these issues is discussed in its own subsection.

G.1 Click on typeable object

The Mind2Web annotator describes the action as a “click” operation on an element that is a typeable object. Figure 9 provides an example where the referenced element is correctly described as “Type Ingredients...”. However, the action “Click” typically applies to clickable elements like buttons or links, whereas the actual element in question is an input field that requires a “Type” action. This discrepancy leads to failures in correctly identifying the action, making it one of the more prevalent issues among the failed samples.

Figure 7. Illustrative examples from the MIND2WEB dataset showing the diversity in tasks and domains.

Figure 8. Duplicate: "Click on Jobs"

Figure 10. Instruction: "Click on 5"

Figure 9. Instruction: "Click on Type Ingredients..."

Figure 11. Equal Flow Trajectory

G.2 Ambiguous target element

Another category of dataset-related failures involves ambiguous descriptions of target elements, which make it difficult to identify the correct interactable elements. In Figure 10, for instance, the instruction "Click on 5" is unclear. A more specific instruction, such as "Click on 5 beds" or "Click on July 5th", would be needed to avoid confusion.

G.3 Box in a Box

Another category of failures we identified can be described as the "box-in-box" issue. This occurs when the annotator selects elements

Figure 12. Input field marked as Ground Truth.

on the screen that correspond to a bounding box in the rendered HTML containing multiple nested elements. While the annotator marks one of these elements as the ground truth, the bounding box often encompasses several interactive elements, leading to potential

